

Building the collective at times of precarity:
precarious labour and its countermovements

Analytical Framework for Studying Work
and its constitutive precarious character under capitalism

Version 1.1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 841164.

Document Control Page	
Project acronym	COLLECTITUDE
Project title	Building the collective at times of precarity: precarious labour and its countermovements
Action	MSCA-IF
Grant no.	841164
Starting Date	01/01/2020
Duration	24 months
Document type	Research Deliverable (D4.4)
Description	Development of the final model/ analytical framework and research agenda for the study of work
Version	1.2
Submission date	15/02/2022
Author	Joana S. Marques
Contributors	Luísa Veloso, Ana Luísa Martinho, Carlota Quintão

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Introduction

The present report was drafted as part of the analytical framework of the project *COLLECTITUDE - Building the collective at times of precarity: precarious labour and its countermovements*. It is based on the literature report *A Conceptual Review of Precarity* (Marques and Veloso 2020), which provides a critique of precarity and acknowledges it as constitutive of capitalist work. Therefore, the present framework can be more broadly understood as an analytical framework for studying work under capitalism. It proposes to use the concept and debate on precarity as a way of feeding into ongoing discussions on the role and place of work (and social protection) in contemporary societies, seeking to contribute to more transformative and imaginative ways of rethinking people's work and livelihoods. After all, the conceptions of precarity also frame the struggles and alternatives, from demands for jobs creation and access to wage labour, even if to integrate an increasingly precarious labour market, to more radical critiques of capitalism and proposals of non-market oriented solutions.

Empirically, this framework draws on evidence from the comparative analysis of the arts sector and the construction sector in Portugal (and, complementarily, of neighbouring fields of archaeology and architecture), analysing their political and economic structuring at the macro level, their specific sectoral configurations, and, on the other hand, the respective responses in terms of collective forms of workers organization, which may integrate Polanyi-like countermovements.¹

This framework also builds on the collective reflection developed at A3S² on the field of social and solidarity economy and all forms of civil society collective organization, seeking to consolidate a structured approach to the sector and to promote the capacity building of the sector's organizations and professionals and the joint construction of a collective project with varied actors on the field.

After briefly outlining the theoretical and empirical backgrounds, the analytical framework is then proposed for advancing the study of precarity (and the prospects of overcoming it) within different forms of work and economic practices, presenting its principles, features, and main dimensions.

¹ According to Polanyi, "For a century the dynamics of modern society was governed by a double movement: the market expanded continuously but this movement was met by a countermovement checking the expansion in definite directions" (Polanyi 2001 [1944], p. 136). This countermovement is constructed in response and to protect society from the excesses of the market.

² A3S is the Research & Development association that hosted the COLLECTITUDE project. It is dedicated to the promotion and capacity-building of Social and Solidarity Economy organizations and professionals, operating itself as work cooperative (see a3s.webnode.pt).

Theoretical background

In the state-of-the-art it is possible to differentiate various approaches to precarity, which unveil dominant preconceptions within current debates and contribute to supporting more empirically grounded and less normative approaches.

Three major lines of thought are consistently referenced across the literature on precarity define it in fundamentally different ways: as a labour condition (Bourdieu 1998; Kalleberg 2009; Millar 2017); as a class category (Standing 2011); as an ontological experience of human existence (Butler 2004; Lorey 2015).

Contesting the ideological construction of wage labour as an idealized livelihood model and, relatedly, of precarity as a novel, atypical phenomenon, many authors show that insecurity in labour and life is constitutive of capitalist development, inside and outside wage labour (Denning 2010; Kasmir 2018; Neilson and Rossiter 2008). Therefore, we need to inquire the common assertion of the equivalence wage labour and dignity (Millar 2017) and better understand the forms and mechanisms of precarity, but also the factors and mechanisms that influence workers agency (Kalleberg 2009).

On another level, there is a distinction between broad conceptions of precarity that recognise the many dimensions and sites of precariousness in contemporary life and narrow conceptions focused on specific labour relations, which has been defined as a “contrast between precarity-in-work and precarity-in-life” (Parfitt and Barnes 2020). Narrower conceptions that restrict it to a limited set of dimensions or quantitative criteria, such as particular forms of employment, have the value of enhancing measurability and comparability, but miss more subjective experiences and mechanisms of precarity, which may be captured in a more qualitative way. In turn, qualitative research often fails to account for representativeness, which may be addressed by building linkages between cases and national surveys, while cross-national research is also crucial to account for cross-country variations (Gallie 2019).

As regards the Portuguese labour market, Carmo et al. (2021) identify a trend towards increasing diversity and complexity of professional paths, establishing a typology of labour market participation profiles, which is marked by overlaps, intersections and interdependencies between professional paths profiles.

In sum, different authors argue for the notion of precarisation as a process, rather than a fixed condition (Mallett 2020) and for the need of a relational approach to precarity rooted in the analysis of specific labour conditions (Alberti et al. 2018; Denning 2010; Kasmir 2018; Millar 2017; Pulignano 2019).

Empirical background

The comparative analysis of the arts sector and the construction sector in Portugal was justified, on the one hand, by the objective conditions of precarity faced by both, as well as the preponderance of project work and, on the other hand, by a set of contrasting features, notably in terms of education levels (low versus high); production processes

(labour-intensive versus skill-intensive); social composition (lower class vs middle-upper class); and differing traditions of collective organization and action. The research sought to analyse their political and economic structuring at the macro level, their specific sectoral configurations and prevailing employment relations, and the collective forms of workers organization that have emergent in the last decades.

The event of the Covid-19 pandemic has also allowed to observe how different sectors of society were impacted unevenly: in Portugal, construction workers kept working when most society went under quarantine, while unions were not able to reach these unprotected workers due to the imposed social distancing; art workers, on the other hand, were among the first to stop and the last to return to work and the sector's structural precarity has been chronically exposed, before the absence of government response, triggering a persistent process of labour organizing.

The construction sector

The construction industry is a labour-intensive sector characterized by providing employment for those with little education or skill, often from the poorer sections of society (International Labour Organization 2001). Its production process has become increasingly fragmented, based on complex subcontracting chains, as well as of the use of agency workers, self-employment and transient employment (Danaj and Sippola 2015), but it has not always been the case in the past. In Portugal, in the 1980s and 1990s, medium-sized and large companies used to be predominant, integrating in their staff as salaried workers a whole range of professions: "They had everything from the cook to the cleaning lady!" (interview with construction union Omega, December 2020). To adapt to the competition of the European free market, Portuguese construction companies have adopted a strategy based on downsizing workers and outsourcing various work stages, through a division of labour based on long subcontracting chains and temporary work agencies. This has resulted in the fragmentation and flexibilization of employment relations, with increasingly temporary, mobile and insecure jobs. The global economic crisis of 2008 has further accelerated this process, through the implementation of austerity measures leading to labour deregulation and devaluation (Leite et al. 2014). As such, the macro economic and political context has had structuring impacts at the organizational level and on employment relations, as well as on the working and living conditions.

The construction industry is also characterized by high labour mobility, since it is a sector in which production sites cannot be moved to other countries in order to lower costs; instead workers have to be mobile. In Portugal labour mobility in the sector has become a mode of regulation (Marques et al. 2021), with a long tradition, comprising both internal mobility through daily or weekly commuting and cross-border mobility (often alternating with other activities particularly related to family farming) – associated to a certain kind of “nomadism” (Pinto and Queiroz 1996). In face of the low wages paid in Portugal, mobility abroad has resulted in high labour shortage over the last years and, thereafter, high levels of illegality, comprising informal work and illegal migrants, which is pointed as a major issue in the country: “In the field of construction in Portugal, we

think that 40% of workers are illegal, it is not precarious, it is illegal!" (interview with construction union Beta, September 2020).

As regards, the prospective level and alternative forms of organizing, it should be noted that in the past there was a relevant movement of cooperatives in the sector, such as the historic *Cooperativa dos Pedreiros* (Masons' Cooperative), founded in 1914, and different experiments that emerged in the aftermath of the Carnation Revolution of 25 April 1974. However, over the last decades no collective forms of workers organization have emerged. It is in the related field of architecture that we find relevant new initiatives, through architects that have organized collectively against the dominant paradigm of work exploitation in the sector and the hegemony of star architects.

The arts sector

As regards the arts sector, it is inversely composed by predominantly qualified professionals (the majority having a tertiary level, both in Portugal and the EU, according to Eurostat data), but on the other hand, art workers have been considered precursor to forms of labour hyper-flexibility (Menger 2003). Discontinuous modes of production are the norm, often assuming the form of individual projects (a show, a film) (Colbert 2011), and involving heterogenous profiles of workers (directors, producers, managers, musicians, actors, performers, mediators, audio-visual technicians, roadies...), which may or not be carried out under temporary employment relations. In Portugal, the performing arts have been predominantly organised around permanent artistic teams to which guest artistic teams and technicians were added within specific projects (see, for instance, Borges 2007, on the Portuguese theatre world). However, the Portuguese state, as a major funder, employer and regulator, has contributed to the deconstruction of labour-related rights and the precarisation of work, through the underfunding of culture (against its public nature and the enshrinement as a right in the Constitution), outsourcing of public management, and the normalization of the independent workers regime and bogus self-employment in the sector. The dependence on intermittent public funding makes that arts organizations operate under continuous financial stress, struggling to provide adequate working conditions. Official data show the decrease of wage workers and increase of self-employed workers, which is much higher in the arts than in the average of all economic activities.

Another dimension of precarity, as identified by Pulignano (2019), is the strong dependence on unpaid work, inside and outside wage labour, which was mentioned by various interviewees: rehearsals/ preparatory work, traineeships, establishing an online presence, applying to calls and competing for projects often in vain, working unsocial hours. This author shows how unpaid activities increasingly underlie paid employment as a source of "value" creation in a deregulated labour market.

The sector's precarity has been exacerbated and exposed by the economic crisis that initiated in 2008 and of the pandemic crisis that initiated in 2020. These macro level contexts have facilitated a framing process (Benford and Snow 2000) of this situation as unequal and unjust, and also the affirmation of the subjectivity as workers, art workers,

and their awareness as a collective, despite the heterogeneity of professions and work situations, resulting in the growth of the sector's union and professional organizations: "One thing we did from the beginning was not to use the term 'artist' and use the term 'worker', 'culture worker', which includes from the technician, front of house/ ushers, to the artist. And this designation is very important so that we can think of our needs and specificities as a class, a working class, because that's what we're fighting for, for that statute. We are all workers!" (interview with Alpha informal professional group, July 2021).

At the same time, despite the preponderance of project work, various types of work collectives have emerged in recent years (Marques and Veloso 2022), such as nonprofit cultural associations, which is the norm in the Portuguese context, related to the ideal of associated work, but corresponding to varied situations (including bogus associations) that reveal different constraints, challenges and survival strategies: "It's a romantic idea, the idea of the association, but at the same time it's a false romanticism because in fact it's just a legal form to replace something that doesn't exist" (interview with Z Collective, May 2021).

New cooperative models for independent workers (freelancers) have also emerged in recent years, who assume independent work and temporariness as desired and planned, providing a common structure for the management and production of independent individual projects. In some cases, as shown by Loacker (2013), there is a subjection to the neoliberal governmentality, associated to the widely spread belief that "one consciously chooses uncertain and underpaid working conditions – because they offer autonomy, variation and self-determination" (p. 139); in others it is a strategy of tackling a system that is unjust. It should also be mentioned the case of social and community-oriented cooperatives, concerned with the surrounding communities and with the work inclusion of vulnerable people excluded from the formal labour market and social protection.

The different forms of organizing reveal different constraints, challenges and strategies of survival and adaptation: if, on the one hand, they present proposals for the construction of a collective project, on the other hand, they are also subject to processes of precarity and commodification.

The contrasting cases analysed also form a basis from which to build an approach to a wider analytical framework.

Relational analytical framework

The presented theoretical and empirical background shows how precarity is multilevel, multidimensional, relational, and processual. In this section, we propose an analytical framework to tackle these multiple layers for advancing the study of precarity (and the prospects of overcoming it) within different forms of work and economic practices.

We begin by outlining a set of principles for precarity studies research drawing from the previous sections.

Principles for Precarity Studies Research

The critique of precarity provides the context for the development of the current analytical framework as a broad approach for social science research. It is based on the following principles:

1. *Relational approach.* Although research generally focuses on specific topics and phenomena, their full comprehension should be informed by the understanding of their embeddedness in multiple social relations and broader processes (see Polanyi 2001 [1944]), at all levels.
2. *Multi-level approach.* The study of precarity, like any social phenomenon, comprises examining the different ways in which macro (social, political, economic environment), meso (organizations, workplaces) and micro (individuals, objective and subjective experiences) levels are connected and mutually structured.
3. *Processual approach.* Precarity should be understood as a multi-dimensional process, rather than a fixed condition, rooted in concrete experiences and territories and in specific historical dynamics of capitalism, and also influenced by the agency of social actors, whose causal mechanisms should be explained.
4. *Interdisciplinary approach.* Social sciences research has a lot to gain by expanding their horizons beyond single academic disciplines and entailing an inter and transdisciplinary perspectives.
5. *Empirically grounded approach.* Research agendas need to commit to systematic empirical investigation, which reflects the complexity of social phenomena within the dynamics of capitalist systems, when possible, building linkages between qualitative, in-depth knowledge and quantitative, extensive studies.
6. *Non-normative approach.* Researchers need to inquire widespread assertions, such as regarding wage labour as identical to decent work/ dignity and devaluing other forms of work, livelihood and economic practice.
7. *Imaginative and prospective approach.* Researchers could engage with more imaginative ways of thinking, beyond existing categories and paradigms, also seeking to map the range of livelihood and economic practices people take up, the alliances they pursue, the organisational forms they innovate (Kasmir 2018), and to generate scientific knowledge relevant to the collective project of challenging various forms of human oppression (Wright 2010), supporting the fight against precarity inside and outside the workplace and envisioning new possibilities.
8. *Accessible, open approach.* The knowledge produced by social sciences is designed to improve people's social and material conditions, therefore it (and its instruments) should be accessible to society at large, through open science

frameworks and by disseminating it in suitable forms to civil society organizations, governments, business, and the general public.

The framework

Drawing on the conceptual landscaping in the field of precarity studies and the interconnection of the research principles outlined above, we propose the present relational analytical framework, which identifies the four levels of analysis: macro; meso/ organisational; micro; and prospective. These four levels are interdependent and, as such, in addition to being considered separately on their own account, they are also to be analysed in combination in relation to each other. Figure 1 attempts a simplified representation.

Evidence gathered from secondary literature and from the empirical work in the arts and construction sectors as allowed to identify several key dimensions inside each levels which are listed in the figure and were used to develop the framework. The qualitative data collected was subject to content analysis, using computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (*MaxQDA*). The coding process used categories taken from past studies but also, undertook an inductive approach, inspired by the grounded theory tradition, aiming at generating new insights to go beyond current state-of-art. The resulting complete code system that resulted from applying this framework to a set of cases in the arts sector and the construction sector in Portugal (and, complementarily, the neighbouring fields of archaeology and architecture), is included in Appendix 1.³

³ In line with the open science principle, the resulting code system (including explanatory memos) is available at COLLECTITUDE project Open Access repository ([Zenodo](#)) in different formats (xlsx, ods, mtr) to enhance its re-use by other researchers.

Figure 1. Relational Framework Scheme

The framework proposes that the specific focus on one level or one phenomenon is informed by the remaining inter-related levels.

Understanding the Macro and transnational processes

The first level entails analysing the socioeconomic and political context of precarity and its macro-level mechanisms and respective implications, notably the transformations in the organisation of work and social dialogue and the role of governments and social partners in the face of changing realities of work. Drawing on Wright Mills, social scientists role is to "understand the nature of the present epoch, to outline its structure and to discern the major forces at work within it" (Mills 2000 [1959], p. 152), in this case, the social forces and institutions that produce precarity. It may include the analysis of

the institutional context and the role of the state (including that of specific policies or regulatory frameworks); geopolitics, such as international competition and insertion in particular regional and geopolitical dynamics (e.g. the EU framework); the economic context, such as specific moments of crisis or growth; the social context, including the structures that define the social background of possibilities (e.g. gender, race) and the normative takes; or the specific sectoral and territory contexts.

Studying the Meso (organizations)

The meso level entails the analysis of the organisational framework for different forms of work, livelihood and economic practice, including examining how forms of workers' organisation are changing in response to current social, political and technical transformations. It may consider the specific organizational contexts; the scope of and specific forms of employment relations and working conditions; work organization (division of labour; decision-making processes); and the different resources used (market; non-market; non-monetary). The boundaries of what is possible at the organizational level are structured by the macro level dynamics but also influenced by the agency of social actors.

Analysing the Micro

This level is about examining how precarity (or inversely the forms of resistance to it and proposed alternatives) unfold at the level of the individual and across different dimensions, impacting differently men and women, social and family relations, the subjective experiences (e.g. stress, exhaustion, anguish), the living conditions (such as access to welfare, educational decisions), as well as social engagement.

Engaging the Prospective

Finally, the prospective level is concerned with the future of work and society, reimagining work and social relations. It entails mapping the range of livelihood and economic practices people take up, circuits of self-production and non-monetary exchange, their main struggles, the collective identities developed, the forms of collective action, the alliances they engage, the organisational forms they innovate, and how they envision alternative forms of production and circulation. It also entails critically examining the proposed alternatives and emancipatory movements, notably the why and how they are transformative or reinforce the status quo and the extent to which they are exclusive (benefiting a specific group) or inclusive (benefiting society as a whole).

This is also contingent on specific policy interventions and institutional innovation which should be elaborated, notably in terms of the possibilities of universal social protection dissociated from people's participation in the (labour) market.

Final Remarks

We hope that recognition of the distinctiveness and interdependence of these four levels and respective dimensions of work and precarity provides a basis for addressing fundamental questions relating to the nature and dynamics of transformations of work within a broader and deeper analytical framework, at the same time contributing to the critical questioning of the status of work, in its different forms (productive or reproductive, formal or informal, paid or unpaid, market or socially oriented), in contemporary capitalist societies.

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Appendixes

Appendix 1. Code System

Code System
I. Macro level
1.1. Institutional context/Role of the State
1.1.1. Institutional mediation
Dismantling public institutions
Public procurement
Funder
Employer
Unclear definition of competences
Erosion of labour lexicon
Bureaucratic state
1.1.2. Regulatory & tax regime
Polluter-pays principle in Archaeology
Unions Regulation
Labour devaluation
Labour Code
Lack of protection for unsocial working hours in the arts
Social Protection
Independent vs Employed work
Proliferation of laws
Normalization of the "Green receipts" regime
Adverse tax regime for cooperatives
Legal procedures
French Intermittent regime
1.1.3. Policy interventions
Proclamation of culture in the Constitution
Devaluation of Cultural Policy
Lack of knowledge on the sector
Decay of public cultural institutions
Ministry underfunding
Lack of political will

Centralized cultural policy
1.1.4.Social dialogue
1.2.Geopolitics
International competition
Erasmus Programme
Portuguese speaking countries
EU funds
EU competition regulations
EU free movement
1.3.Economic context
1.3.1.Crisis
Pandemic crisis (2020-2021)
Telecommuting
No access to emergency measures
Union growth
Focus on the local level
Extreme precarity
Redistribution of resources
Supporting the most vulnerable
Closure of activities
Constraints to unions work
Difficulties in maintaining employed workers
Uncertainty regarding labour legislation
Work-life balance
Additional work demand
No significant Covid outbreaks
Risks & fear
Covid-related measures or their Absence
Lay-off
Activities that kept working
Suspension of labour mobility
Economic crisis (2008-2016)
Destruction of the economic fabric
High volume of work
Recovery
Labour struggles
Culture devaluation

Labour devaluation & unemployment
Labour drain/ mobility
Suspension of economic activities
Bankruptcy of companies
1.3.2.Growth
Real estate boom
1.3.3.Major economic actors
1.4.Social context
1.4.1.Structuring social background
1.4.2.Normative takes
1.5.Sectoral Context
1.5.1.Employment relations
Public sector
Major employer sector
Subcontracting
Poor working conditions
Mobility
Migrant work
Unpaid work
Multijobbing
Working times/ Overtime
Unsocial working hours
Informality/ Illegality
Plateau
Dismantling employment relations
Bogus associations
Professionalization deficit
Lack of cooperative tradition
Stable employment as exception
Uncertainty
Prearity as norm
1.5.2.Pay regulation
Collective bargaining agreement
Low wages
1.5.3.Competitiveness
Digitalization
Local impact

Foreign competition
Lack of expertise
Dependence on public works
Crisis impact
Letter-box companies
Labour drain & labour shortage
Small size of companies
Lack of public export office
1.5.4.Structuring institutions or Works
Soares da Costa
Mota-Engil
Foz Côa
Barragem do Sabor
Alqueva
São Carlos
Casa da Música
1.5.5.Norms
1.5.6.Self- and Hetero-Perceptions
Construction as a national vocation
Arts vs Construction
Devaluation of the sector
The best construction workers
'Subsidy-junkies'
Independent work as a choice
Art is work
Art is not work
1.5.7.Voice
Lack of data
Union support
Lack of awareness of rights
Historic unions
Lack of unity
Limited representation/ voice of precarious workers
1.5.8.Professions expound
Plasterer
Engineers
Hodman

Foreman
Archaeology
Architecture
Crane operator
Construction-related
Actor/ Theatre
Cinema
Audio-visual technicians
Music-related
Roadie
Cultural Production
Finding solutions
Multi-tasking
Artistic involvement
Executive production
Strategic management
Administrative management
Bringing a new look to the profession
Indispensable for arts work
Production is life
Dance
Open field
1.5.9.Education & Training
Skills development
Lack of initial training opportunities
Overqualified
Skills recognition and certification
Compulsory training in companies
Low education level
1.7.Territory context
Urban centrality
Social and cultural wealth
Lack of opportunities in small-medium sized cities
Countryside as precarious territory
II. Micro level
2.1.Professional path
Experience with Star Architect

Early exit from archaeology profession
Family business/ Industry
From other areas to the culture field
From the culture field to other areas
Previous experiences of precarity
2.2. Subjective experiences of precarity
Lack of recognition or prospects
Anguish/ Despair
Stress
Exhaustion
2.3. Precarity-in-life
2.3.01. Family
Most don't have kids
Respect for family time/ responsibilities
Insecurity to have children
2.3.02. Work–life balance
Difficult balance
Inconstancy
2.3.03. Access to welfare
2.3.04. Satisfaction
2.3.05. Social Mobility
2.3.06. Educational decisions
Change of Education field
2.3.07. Health
2.3.08. Solidarity
2.3.09. Community
2.3.10. Social Ties
2.3.11. Endebtness/ Access to credit
2.4. Mobility
2.5. Gender issues
2.5.1. Roles
2.5.2. Sexual division
2.5.4. Working conditions
Diverse perspectives
2.5.5. Opportunities
Equal treatment and opportunities
2.5.6. Impacts

2.5.7. Access to funding
2.5.8. Harassment
2.6. Individual motivations
Trajectory of precarity
Finding new solutions to social issues
Passion for culture
Supporting younger people
Social/ Political engagement
Work ethic
Working collectively
2.7. Relationship with the workplace
Common space as a driver
Co-working space as opportunity for networking
2.8. Relationship with work object/content
Dedication
Constantly finding new solutions
Place of discovery & self-expression
III. Meso Level - Organizations
3.0. Organizational contexts
1.6.1. Employment relations
1.6.2. Managerial regimes
1.6.3. Cooperative tradition
1.6.4. Resistance
Workers solidarity
3.1. Work collectives
3.1.01. Types
Dual collective
Platform cooperativism
Self-employment cooperative (freelancers)
Shared service/ Independent producers collective
Social/ Community-oriented cooperative
Worker cooperative
3.1.02. Legal form
Production Cooperative
Services cooperative
Cultural and social cooperative
Cultural Cooperative

Cultural Association
3.1.03.Origins
Addressing societal needs
Creating opportunities outside main cities
Working for low-income groups
Territory & Community roots
Addressing members (workers) needs
Professionalization
Bogus collective
Access to funding
Adaptation to existing framework/ lack of alternatives
Private company
Creating work opportunities/ Escaping migration
Transition between different legal forms
3.1.04FOUNDERS
Previous private company
University colleagues
Previous associative work
Freelancers seeking for alternative employment framework
Philanthropic work/ Voluntarism
Single person
3.1.05.Mission/ Collective purpose
3.1.5.2.Exclusive
Common production structure
Addressing precarity
Access to salaried employment regime
Professionalization
Creating work opportunities for members
3.1.5.1.Inclusive
Critical thinking
Social & economic sustainability
Redistribution of resources
Linking culture and local (countryside) communities
Work opportunities at the margins
Local development & territory regeneration
Social inclusion
Social transformation

Proximity & Social participation
3.1.06.References/ Models
Multidisciplinary collective
European freelancers cooperative
Production-Consumption cooperatives
Other examples
Worker Cooperative
3.1.07.Members
3.1.7.1.Types
Other collective organizations
Investors
Voluntary workers
Consumers/ Clients
Non-member staff
Employed workers
Independent Workers
Board Members
3.1.7.2.Conditions for new members
Openness
Reciprocity
Limits of the structure
Independence/ Individuality
Affinity
3.1.08.Services provided to members
Contracting and Social Security affiliation
Career development
Financial and administrative management/ Invoicing
Discounts
Collective projects/ Grants
Shared structure
3.1.09.Activities
Design & Construction
Intervention in the public space
Technical advice
Housing projects
Socio-cultural mediation
Festival

Community centre
Artist in residency
Coffee shop
Tourist accommodation
Supporting professionalization & associativism
Diversification of activities
Education/community projects
Audiovisual production/publisher
Artist Management
Talent scouting
Archive
Research
Artistic creation
Cultural programming
3.1.10.Surplus
Reserve fund
Reinvestment
Redistribution
3.1.11.Constraints
Lack of framing for community work
Tourism dependency
Lack of Impact Assessment of culture
Lack of structuring, integrated approach
Gentrification
Ambiguity of the cooperative form
Precarizing the work of non-members
Tension between budgets and artistic ambitions
Tensions between collective and individual goals
Lack of conditions to ensure Labour security
3.2.Employment Relations
3.2.1.Forms of employment relationships
Bogus self-employment
Indefinite contract
Internship with employment perspective
Internship
Long-term unemployment
Multi-party employment relationship

Multijobbing
Outsourcing
Part-time work
Self-employment as cooperative/employed work
Self-employment as independent workers
Temporary employment
3.2.2.Wages/ Income
Differentiated per effort rate
Uncompetitive wages/ Brain drain
Different sources
Fair wages
Other benefits
Income from outside the organization
According to proposed budgets
No bonuses or salary increase
Dependent on each one's projects
Reasonable wages
3.2.3.Unpaid work
Unpaid activities remunerated by the collective
Lack of compensation for extra work
Unpaid activities underlying paid employment
3.2.4.Job Security
Dependent on members efforts
Unsuitability
Job security as a priority
Uncertainty
Envisioned security
3.2.5.Working time
Respect for working time
Working by objectives
Flexibility
Unmeasurability
Unsocial working hours
3.2.6.Working intensity
Longer timing due to inexperience
No vacations
High work intensity

Continuous new requests
3.2.7.Voice
Previous experiences in professional organizations
3.2.8.Social protection
Employed worker social protection
Food allowance
Unemployment benefit
Allowances (vacation, Christmas bonus)
Accessing a more favourable regime abroad
Social Insecurity
3.2.9.Risk
Uncertainty of funding
Investment in competing to funding, often in vain
Lack of reserve fund
3.2.10.Training opportunities
Few training opportunities
Continuous training & learning
3.3.Project-work
3.3.1.Types
Hollow
Craft
Precarious
Organizational
3.3.3.Type of temporariness
Precarious
Planned/ desired
3.4.Work organization
3.4.1.Division of labour
Merit based
Proactivity
Per functions/ skills
Flexibility
Invited teams
Working groups
Collaboration/ Cooperation
Variable per project
3.4.2.Role Stability

Simplification of work organization
Adaptability
Inconstancy
Multi-tasking
Against specialization
Rotation of fixed roles/tasks
Stability of specific roles
3.4.3.Tasks
Management of material resources
Cleaning
Cooperator relationship
Accounting
Space management
Booking
Management
Production
Communication
Artistic Creation
Financial management
Administrative
3.4.4.Governance & Decision-making
3.4.4.1.Types of Decision-making
Day-to-day decisions
Focused on each project
Focused on strategic management
3.4.4.2.Procedures
Dynamic
Weekly meetings
Consensus
Concentrated on the Board
Compulsory Procedures (General meetings, board, statutes)
Board rotation
Information sharing
Discussion
3.4.5.Supervision
3.4.5.1.Extent
Collaborative supervision

None
3.4.5.2.Task authority
3.4.5.3.Sanctions
3.4.6.Hierarchy
Experience-based
Required by law
Functional hierarchy
Horizontality
Preponderance of the author/director
3.4.7.Autonomy
3.4.7.1.Degree
1-High autonomy
2-Probably high autonomy
3-Intermediate autonomy
4-Probably intermediate autonomy
5-Low autonomy
6-No autonomy
3.4.8.Management
Shared, trust-based
Manage ambiguity
Business culture
Open process
3.5.Resources & Funding
3.5.1.Types of resources
3.5.1.1.Public/Non-market resources
Multiplicity/ Hybrid areas
Government funding
Municipal or Regional funding
European funds
3.5.1.2.Market resources in the private sector
Own office
Rented space
Individual funds
Services provision/ Sale of good by the organization
Services provision outside the organization
3.5.1.3.Market resources in the SSE
Co-working space

Social business
Percentage on members invoicing (overheads)
Members capital
3.5.1.4.Non-monetary resources (reciprocity, voluntary work)
Loaned spaces
Occupation of public space
Exchange of services
Voluntary work
3.5.2.Material Resources/Mean of production
Without own means of production
Own means of production
3.5.3.Partnerships & Networks
Local communities & stakeholders
Long-term construction/ Social sustainability
Municipality support/ partnership
Professional networks
3.5.4.Financial Situation
Lack of eligibility to Government funding
No loans
Organized and controlled situation
Uncertainty
No margin for extra costs
Lack of stability/ Financial gymnastics
Stability
3.6.Territory
Multicultural hub
National
International
Priority to local hiring
Focus on local community/ territory
Valuing local/regional culture
IV.Prospective level
4.1. Main Struggles
Harrasment
Preserving cultural heritage
Career development
Wages & working conditions

Human dignity
COVID Emergency measures
Addressing precarity
Dynamic
Racism
Gender equality
Crosscutting issues
Specific laws for different professions
1% for Culture
Dealing with existing legal framework
Against Cultural marginalization of the countryside
Access to Labour contract & rights
4.2. Collective Identities
4.2.1. Framing
Archeologists & assistants
Precarious workers
Construction workers
Informal group vs professional organizations
Stable vs Precarious workers
Workers/ Proletarian
Art Workers/ "Trabalhadores da cultura"
Artists vs Technicians
4.2.2. Solidarity
4.2.3. Class
Heterogeneity
Class awareness
4.3. Collective Action
4.3.1. Types
Social Movements
Unionization
Professional organizations
Politics
Other
4.3.2. Levels of engagement
1- High engagement level
2- Intermediate engagement level
3- Low engagement level

4- Past engagement
5- No engagement
4.3.3.Strategies
4.3.3.1.Sectoral
Social media networking
Envisioning concrete alternatives
Protocols
Provision of information & Legal support
Internationalism
Direct contact with workers
Working groups
Horizontality
Organic functioning/ freedom
Plenaries & Meetings with workers
Board rotation
Joining different professional subsectors
4.3.3.2.Cross-Sectoral
Other neighboring sectors
Trade union federation
4.3.3.3.Conflictive
Historic forms of action
4.3.3.4.Cooperative
Cooperation between unions & other movements/organizations
Awareness raising
Social dialogue
4.3.4.Targets
Employers & Managers
Government/ Policy institutions
4.3.5.Resources
Mass media
Support from elected Members of Parliament
Employers & Labour on the same side
Voluntary work
Visibility
Membership
4.3.6.Repertoires
Training and pedagogical measures

Complaint to competent authorities
Campaign
Collective Bargaining
Statements
Demonstrations
Petition
Rally
Marches
Occupations
Road blocks
Vigils
Boycotts
Strike
4.3.7.Constraints
Inexperience
Unions regulation
Employers pressure
Lack of common workplace for the development of solidarities
Lack of awareness
Difficult unionization of precarious, mobile workers
Economic difficulties
Lack of unity
Lack of availability
4.4.Alternative forms of work, livelihood and economic practice
Voluntary work
Mutual aid
Engaging older workers in reskilling efforts
Conditioning public procurement to salaried work
Decent work
Basic income
4.5.Other forms of resistance and innovation
Citizen groups
Multiple affiliations
4.6.Policy Innovation/ Recommendations
Questioning legal models/regimes
Joint responsibility regarding subcontracting chains
Addressing illegal work

Labour inspection
Social protection/ Innovation
Welfare state
Retention of qualified workforce
Public procurement
Valuing work in the third sector
Bottom-up State
Integrated approaches
1% for Culture
Enhancing the value of culture
Stimulus to employment creation
Less bureaucracy and more agility in policy implementation
Decentralizing Cultural policy
Intermittent regime
4.7.Institutional innovation
V. Sociodemographics
5.01.Age
<29
30-39
40-49
50-59
60-69
> 70
5.02.Gender
5.03.Race
5.04.Place of birth
Portuguese Metropolitan Area
African city
Brazilian city
Portuguese medium-sized town (Lisbon Metropolitan Areas)
5.05.Marital status
Married
Single
5.06.Education level
5.6.1.Primary
5.6.2.Secondary
5.6.3.Graduate

5.6.4.PostGraduate
5.07.Education area
Architecture
Archaeology
Visual arts
Cinema
Law
Communication/ Multimedia
Geography/ Urbanism
Performing Arts
5.08.Job
Professor
Architect & urbanist
Archaeologist
Unionist
Choreographer
Musician
Director
Cultural producer/ promoter
Executive producer
Artist
5.09.Employment status
5.10.Employees
5.11.Role
Worker/ Non-member
Treasurer
Board member
President
5.12.Social class
5.12.1.Subjective
Middle class
Worker
Ruling class
No class identity
Entrepreneur/ Leader
Upper middle class/ privileged
Artist

5.12.2.Objective
5.12.3.Professional identity
Cultural promoter
Cultural Producer
Artist
5.12.4.Social capital
5.12.5.Cultural capital
5.12.6.Economic capital